

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

CATALYTIC ACTIVATION DEHYDROALKYLATION BENZENE PROPANE TO SYSTEMS Pt, REO_x/ Al₂O₃ + H-ZEOLITE

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Abstract

The involvement of C₁-C₃ alkanes in the processes of obtaining valuable products is of great theoretical and practical importance. One of the ways to solve this problem is the possibility of catalytic involvement of these alkanes in the alkylation of aromatic compounds. (Y, M, ZSM-5) for the conversion of C₆H₆:C₃H₈ mixtures. The study was carried out on a mechanical mixture of an aluminum-platinum-rhenium catalyst prepared according to a well-known method and H-forms of zeolites (Y, M, ZSM-5).

Formation of products conversion of benzene-propane mixtures MMC (mechanical mixture of catalysts) is accompanied by the occurrence of three reactions: a) the alkylation of benzene; b) the propane dehydrogenation; c) the formation of alkylaromatic hydrocarbons. The course of these reactions depends on the contact conditions of the studied mixtures with MMC. The interaction of propane with benzene proceeds most effectively on a mechanical mixture of catalysts, the components of which are unreduced MReO_x/Al₂O₃ and the H-form of the zeolite, which are carriers of spatially separated redox and acid-base centers. The addition of small amounts of benzene to propane leads to the activation of propane and the formation of hydrogen, the yield of which corresponds to the molar conversion of propane. Depending on the temperature, the distribution of the conversion products of the C₆H₆ : C₃H₈ mixture is characterized by a change in the yields of IPB, n-PB, the sum of other aromatic C₇-C₉ hydrocarbons, and propylene.

Keywords: conversion, C₆H₆ : C₃H₈ mixtures, PtReO_x/Al₂O₃ +H- zeolite, isopropyl benzene, alkylaromatic hydrocarbons

Results of studying the conversion of C₆H₆ : C₃H₈ mixtures MMC showed that only in the presence of benzene MMC has activity in a low temperature (≥ 180 °C) conversion of propane. The introduction of small amounts of benzene into propane (for example, 10 mol %) leads to its transformations and the formation of hydrogen, the molar value of which corresponds to the total molar conversion of propane. Eduction of hydrogen in the conversion of benzene-propane mixtures is a total

reflection of the noted reactions. Conversion C₆H₆ : C₃H₈ mixtures depends on the pretreatment of the catalyst. Eduction hydrogen subjected to standard processing air MMC characterized by a period of activation. This activation period MMC is associated exclusively with the interaction of propane with PtReO_x/Al₂O₃ (APRC) catalyst and, by analogy with methane, may be a consequence of the partial reduction of the metal component of MMC (tab. 1).

Table 1

The effect of the ratio of benzene conversion of propane and a mixture of C₆H₆: C₃H₈. T = 250 °C, V = 500 h⁻¹

Content, mol. %		Conversion, %		The product yield, % C		
C ₆ H ₆	C ₃ H ₈	C ₆ H ₆	C ₃ H ₈	IPB	C ₃ H ₆	ArH
125	100	-	0	-	-	-
250	90	12	1.9	3.6	0.5	-
500	75	14	7.2	6.2	0.7	2.2
750	50	23	7.7	6.4	0.4	2.6
1000	0	0	-	-	-	-

It is seen from Table 1, that the yield of conversion products C₆H₆ : C₃H₈ mixtures depends on their ratio. Changing the molar ratio of C₆H₆: C₃H₈ from 1 : 9 to 1 : 1 leads to an increase in conversion of benzene and C₉ growth ArH composition. Varying the volume speed of from 125 to 1000 h⁻¹ changes as the conversion of components of C₆H₆ : C₃H₈ mixture and distribution of the

reaction products (tab. 2) – below than 500 h⁻¹ is increased yield IPB and formations NPB and ArH with slight amounts of propylene. Increasing the volume speed leads to a monotonic decrease of benzene conversion, while the conversion of propane in the range of V = 125-500 h⁻¹ is reduced, and then increases again with growth the volume speed of from 500 to 1000 h⁻¹.

Table 2

The effect of volume speed rate of reactants on the conversion of benzene-propane mixture at APRC + HY; T = 250 °C

V, h ⁻¹	Conversion, %			Product Yield, %		
	C ₆ H ₆	C ₃ H ₈	IPB	C ₃ H ₆	NPB	ArH
125	18.2	2.7	4.3	0.1	0.3	0.4
250	15.8	2.2	4.0	0.4	0.2	0.1
500	11.4	2.0	3.1	0.6	traces	0
750	10.2	2.9	2.8	1.4	0	0
1000	8.5	5.7	2.3	3.9	0	0

Varying the ratio of metal and acid MMC components leads to a change in the transformation products C₆H₆ : C₃H₈ mixtures. The data show that the type of zeolite influences the conversion of individual components of the reaction mixture and the yield (selectivity) of the reaction products.

References

1. Abasov S.I., Babayeva F.A., Tagiyev D.B., Rustamov M.I.. Low-temperature catalytic alkylation of benzene by propane // Applied Catalysis A: General.

2003, N 251, p. 267-274.

2. Babayeva F.A., Abasov S.I., et al. Transformation of benzene-propane mixtures on Pt,ReO_x/Al₂O₃ catalytic systems // Georgian Chemical Journal, 2004, v. 4, N. 1, p. 28-34.

3. Abasov S.I., Babayeva F.A., et al. Influence of zeolite nature on low-temperature transformations of C₆H₆ : C₃H₈ mixtures on catalytic systems Pt, Re/Al₂O₃ + H-zeolite // Processes of petrochemistry and oil refining. 2004, N. 3 (18), p. 87-93.